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ABSTRACTS

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Identification and characterization of novel drug targets against multidrug resistant bacteria using *in-silico* approaches

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Abstract: The usage of anti-bacterial drugs for extended duration has increased the emergence of multidrug- (MDR) and extensively drug-resistant (XDR) bacterial strains. Therefore, to address the emerging risk of antibacterial resistance the development of compounds with new modes of action that engage unexploited drug targets can be considered. In the current study, tRNA modification enzymes which are known to facilitate the intracellular growth in bacterial strains were identified as novel drug targets. The sequence of these tRNA modification enzymes were fetched from the databases and was further explored for the identification of conserved domain. The *in-silico* structure models were built for the novel tRNA modification sequences and was further validated. Furthermore, the modeled structures of tRNA modification enzymes will be characterized for their binding affinity using molecular dynamics simulation approaches and novel antimicrobial agents with new approach of action will be designed.

Keywords: Multidrug-resistance, tRNA modification, molecular dynamics.

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